

Original Research Article

Perception On Feedback and Reflection Writing by First Year MBBS Students

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ABSTRACT

Background: Reflection writing by undergraduate analyzed as vital element now a days to contribute as important tool to improve medical education and clinical practices for professional development. This study evaluates the gain of reflective writing on boosting writing skills, enhancing motivation, increasing creativity, explored differences in students 'performance and also critical thinking among undergraduate students.

Objective: The objective of this study is to refine the students & faculties to value the necessity for encouraging a 'feedback culture' and furnish practical tips to provide feedback and 'collect feedback' constructively.

Method: Numerous models of providing feedback including Sandwich model, Pendleton Rules & Learning Conversation. Research analysis done in this area indicated that reflection combined with feedback can remarkably aid to self-directed learning & reflective practice. Total 130 undergraduate students have given feedback and reflection writing consisting 10 item questionnaire which was distributed among students.

Result: The results of the study showed the positive outcome of make use of reflective writing in enhancing motivation and self-confidence.

Conclusion: Reflection offers the ability to increase and strengthen learning ability. Further research is needed to identify the attributes of effective feedback, and strategies for encouraging reflective writing practices. Also feedback combined with reflection writing process that can significantly contribute to self-directed learning

Keywords: Feedback, Reflection, Self-Directed Learning

INTRODUCTION

The ability to take a thorough medical history requires competency in interpersonal communication skills and is essential at all levels of medical training¹. Feedback and reflection are tools known to improve communication and improve quality of process as well as outcome. Ability to critically analyze knowledge and experience to achieve deeper meaning and understanding², reflective capacity has been identified as a core clinical competency that allows physicians and expert to be attentive, get new knowledge, skills and addition to attitudes, aid values and communication, curious, self-aware, and willing to recognize and correct errors³.

A feedback is generally followed by reflection by the giver, recipient or both. Feedback is mainly associated with interaction between two persons, mostly teacher and student, doctor and patient etc. whereas, Reflection is a process in which the individual teacher or student, soon after an episode, thinks deep about what exactly happened, why it did happen that way, and what could have been done better. Feedback is to help a person to correct his/her mistakes so as to improve his/ her competence. The meaning and scope of feedback and model have been explained (Table 1 and 2)⁴

"Reflective Writing" is an analytical practice in which the writer describes a real or imaginary scene, interaction, adding a personal reflection on the meaning of the item or incident⁵ whereas, Reflection is a form of personal response

to experiences or on new information which is a processing phase where thinking and learning parallel takes place where there are just questions to explore, not that there is the right or wrong way of reflective thinking⁶. There are various types of reflective cycles which help us with reflective writing by giving a clear idea on how an event or an exercise should be explained and written, e.g. Gibb's Reflective cycle⁷ mentioned in below Figure-1.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This is descriptive study among first year MBBS students of Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences and GK General Hospital, Bhuj, Gujarat, India during 2021-2022. Informed consent was taken from the students.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

First year MBBS Students of GAIMS & GK General Hospital, Bhuj After foundation course.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Students who were absent and not given consent for participation.

Ten Feedback questionnaires were made and validate after consultation with medical education experts. After then all First year who had given consent of participation were asked to fill the questionnaires and give feedback of reflection writing. The result were obtained from the data generated and conclusion were made accordingly.

Table 1: The Meaning and Scope of Feedback

What feedback is about?	What feedback is not about?
Guiding the learner to correct his/her mistakes	Finding fault with the learner
Listening and directing what is right and what is wrong	Telling and judging who is right or who is wrong
Monitoring the progress of the learner	Sitting on the judgment about learner's competence
Encouraging and motivating the learner	De - motivating or threatening the learner with the probable consequences
Briefly specifying the strength and limitations	Making an elaborate list of deficiencies
Informing the learner's strengths and weaknesses privately	Exposing the learner's weakness to the whole class
Telling the points immediately	Lodging a complaint later
Planning a future strategy	Digging about the past

Figure-1: Gibb's Reflective Cycle

Table 2: Few Models of Giving Feedback

	Instructor's Role	Learners Role
1. Sandwich Model	Appreciates what was done well	Listens to comments
	Points out deficiencies	Listens to comments
	Reinforces strength again	Listens to comments
2. Pendleton Rules		
a. Positive aspects or Strengths	Listens	Describes what he/she did well
	Amplifies & adds to what learner confessed	
b. Negative aspects or Deficiencies	Amplifies & adds to what learner confessed	Describes what he/she did well
c. Final Summary	Adds and complements	Summarizes major highlights
3. Learning Conversation		
Instructor initiates conversation with a learner looking back his/her performance in a particular event individually or in class		
The learner narrates his/her strengths of weaknesses & experience which he/she felt		
The learner identifies the key issues		
The demonstrator survey these matters with the whole class & collect inputs		
plan of action is decided and informed to learner to try next time		
The learner analyses the action plan in his/her routine practice		
The learner describes his/her experience this time...and the conversation continues.....		

RESULTS

Out of 150 batch of students, 130 students had given responses of questionnaires were being asked which have been tabulated in Table -3

Table 3: Feedback of Reflection Writing from MBBS Students

Sr. No.	Question	Strong agree (%)	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strong disagree
1	This reflection method helped you to understand topic	105 (80.76)	25 (19.23)	0	0	0
2	This Reflection method is enjoyable	122 (93.84)	6 (4.61)	2 (1.5)	0	0
3	This Reflection method is Useful learning tool	122 (93.84)	7 (5.38)	0	1 (0.76)	0
4	This Reflection method should be part of routine course	114 (87.69)	14 (10.76)	1 (0.76)	0	1 (0.76)
5	This Reflection method contribute to your overall learning better than classic lecture	8 (6.15)	109 (83.84)	10 (7.69)	1 (0.76)	2 (1.5)
6	You will be happy if this Reflection method is used again for you	107 (82.30)	8 (6.15)	10 (7.69)	4 (3.07)	1 (0.76)
7	You will recommend other students to undergo this Reflection method	120 (92.30)	9 (6.9)	1 (0.76)	0 (0)	0 (0)
8	This Reflection method is waste of time.	1 (0.76)	2 (1.5)	6 (4.61)	19 (14.61)	102 (78.46)
9	This Reflection method is too difficult.	2 (1.5)	0 (0)	6 (4.61)	24 (18.46)	98 (75.38)
10	This Reflection method is too complicated.	1 (0.76)	4 (3.07)	8 (6.15)	19 (14.61)	98 (75.38)

DISCUSSION

This study aims to establishing an enjoyable learning environment, involving medical students in the process of planning and help students to establish their own learning goals, making them to design their own strategies of learning and aids medical students to evaluate their own learning by process of reflection. 93.84% of students had strongly agreed that the reflection writing method is enjoyable and useful learning tools in medical education which is outlined in table-3. Whereas 80.76% and 87.69% highlighted that reflection method helped students to understand topic and should be part of routine course respectively which are depicted in table-3. 1.5% students were agreed that reflection writing method is waste of time whereas 78.46% students strongly disagree on this point. 75.38% students strongly disagreed on that reflection writing method is too difficult and complicated, depicted in table-3.

Also 92.30% students had given in their response that they shall recommend other students to undergo this Reflection writing method.

CONCLUSION

Reflection offers the ability to increase and strengthen learning ability. Further research is needed to identify the attributes of effective feedback, and strategies for encouraging reflective writing practices. Also feedback combined with reflection writing process that can significantly contribute to self-directed learning.

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